

African Cultural Tourism Products in the Digital Growth of the Economy of Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria as a nation in African, is endowed with rich cultural products from the various ethnic groups. The cultural tourism products if well harnessed have the tourism potentials in improving and sustaining the economy of the nation. These cultural products and tourism potentials, appears not have been making the desired impacts on the economy. The dearth of the products on digital devices in Nigeria in the past, crippled the gains and progresses on African cultural tourism products in the economy growth. It becomes imperative for the various ethnic groups and government at all levels in Nigeria to improve and ensure effective delivery on the rich cultural products and tourism potentials, via digitalization. As well to ensure a structure that will create path-ways for Nigeria economic growth. Qualitative research method is adopted in this study to explore the expressions of scholars on African cultural products heritages in Nigeria and how application of information communication technology on these cultural products and tourism potentials can aid economy growth in the nation. This will reveal the abundance endowed African cultural produces and tourism potentials in all the various ethnic groups in Nigeria and digitalization of the products vital in the growth of the economy. Thus, the study advocates the digitalization of the nation's cultural products heritages towards developing and sustaining the tourism industry in the digitalized economy of Nigeria.

Keywords: Cultural Products, Tourism, Growth, Economy, Digitalization

Introduction

African continent is rich with cultural products from the various nations that constitute the continent. Nigeria, being a nation in Africa, is endowed with cultural heritages from the various ethnic groups and regions of the nation. As expressed by Lucia Aiello and Claudia Cacia, Africa has rich tradition of Arts and crafts.¹ This implies that African arts and crafts find expression in a variety of wood carvings, brass and leather artwork. The arts and crafts also include sculpture, paintings, pottery, ceremonies, religious activities, dressing, cuisine, music, dance, language etc. The cultural products have the potentials to boost and sustain cultural tourism and tourism industry in Nigeria and Africa. Burkart A and Medlik S. remark that tourism is viewed as a “leisure activity, which involves a discretionary use of time and money and recreation is often the main purpose for participation in tourism.”² The leisure activity in a tourism destination is spurred by the desire tourist have to experience the phenomena that are different from those available in their home environment. One of such experiences is the cultural products from other countries / nations of the world. This then makes the understanding of cultural tourism to entail “a participation of indigenous peoples and their traditional cultures: including land, river, lake, mountains, religion, dressing, building, environment, dance / music, cuisines, festivals / resources right to help meet their own goals of independence and cultural survival.”³ In other words, Smith S.L.J assert that “tourism in Nigeria / Africa centres on the people’s cultural heritages and other attractions that are identified and harnessed for tourist leisure, recreation and satisfaction.”⁴

The dearth of these cultural tourism products on the digital devices in Nigeria, in the past, hampered the contributions these cultural products are meant to impact in the growth of the economy of the nation. It weakened the e-commerce, e-market places, streaming platforms and connection of the cultural products to global environment / economic where millions around the nation / world can take part to participate in the activities of the African cultural tourism products. The economic viability of these African cultural tourism products appears unknown to most communities, states and nations where they are predominantly situated. In some cultural tourism

destinations where they are identified, harnessing the cultural products for digitalization becomes awkward. This is due to non-literate on digital devices by the cultural tourism host destination practitioners. Thus, dearth on the cultural tourism products on the digital economy of the state and nation is been created.

It becomes inevitable in the digitalized global economy operation for the cultural products not impacting on the growth of the nation's economy. This becomes the thrust of this paper in exploring the various ethnic groups / regions in Nigeria cultural products, harnessing the products to enhance effective delivery on the rich cultural products and tourism potentials of Nigeria through digitalization. Achieving the digitalization of the African cultural tourism products will ensure a structure that will create pathways for the growth of Nigerian economy as well ease the process of marketing the goods and services derived from the cultural products from the various cultural heritages in the nation. In addition to this, the use of digital devices in African cultural tourism products will show case the rich cultural heritages of the people to the world digital economy that are potent in boosting the economy activities / potentials of communities, states, nations and government at all levels.

To achieve this, Antonio Gramsci's theory of cultural hegemony approach is adopted in this study to ascertain the dominant impacts cultural values have made on the people that has aided in them maintaining their cultural values through the use of the cultural institutions without forcing or coercion. And how the use of cultural ideologies fostered an influence on other minor ethnic groups in accepting the cultural products from the major ethnic groups in Nigeria as cultural heritages that would boost the growth of the digital economy of the country.⁵ Expressions of scholars on African cultural products and tourism potentials, some cultural products heritages in Nigeria and its application on the information communication technology on these products are viewed. The approach adopted, revealed the abundance endowed African Cultural Tourism products and tourism potentials in all the various ethnic groups / regions in Nigeria and that the digitalization of the cultural products are vital in the growth of the economy of the nation. This shall be elucidated in the theoretical framework on cultural products, some selected cultural products in Nigeria, digitalization of the cultural products and tourism sites and growth of the economy.

Theoretical Framework on Cultural Products

Theories abound in the discourse on culture as in determining the African cultural tourism products and tourism potentials in the growth of digital economy. One of such theories is the Klejto Cikaj exploration of Antonio Gramsci's theory on cultural Hegemony.⁶ Central to his exploration and notion on cultural hegemony which he asserts is „Ominipresent in Civil society.⁷ For institutions of civil society, the ruling class spreads its moral, political and social values which are instilled by the ruled class which fosters the state to keep her subjects at bay without using violent force.⁸ Abdellatif El Aidi and Yahya Yechouti in expatiating the cultural hegemony, remark that the theory enables the dominant classes maintain their rule through the use of cultural institution to establish the consent of the subaltern classes.⁹ In other words, the dominant class instead of using force and coercion, ideologies are developed to manipulate other classes in the society into accepting their status as subaltern.¹⁰

Although, Eugenio Enrique, Cortes Ramirez, reasoned that cultural hegemony to be broader than that of ideology.¹¹ They expressed that cultural hegemony on cultural products refers to the construction process of the collective experience; of the modelling of meanings; from the development of values, the creation of world conceptions and of the moral, cultural and intellectual direction of society, through cultural products.¹² Adopting this theory as John Story observed on the cultural hegemony implies that „every ethnic groups / regions in Nigeria that have come into existence on the cultural tourism products in the world of economic production, creates together with itself cultural identity, one or more level of cultural intellectuals which gives its homogeneity and awareness of its cultural values not only in the economic but also in the social religious and political fields.¹³ What John Story observed then implies that those in the religious arts, sculptures /crafts etc in the cultural products production, creates alongside in the cultural tourism products production, and political economy that emerges as new cultural as well a new legal system in the regions/nations.

It is on this premise that the theory further fosters the retention of cultural intellectual identities by some persons in the regions of the cultural tourism products productions. It implies that those with the in-depth grasp on the cultural tourism products heritage / values, sustain the rich cultural heritages without caving into the exotic cultural influences on their cultural identities. In another vein, the cultural intellectual retains the cultural heritage values against social and modernization forces on the people's cultural identities. Thus, they maintain a long-time intellectual supremacy which aid the new generations to assimilate the cultural tourism products values.

Critics to cultural hegemony theory assert the dominance and subordination of minority ethnic group cultural products heritages within a region / nation. T.J. Lears observed, that the theory that encourages intellectual cultural identities does not enable other cultural identities from the minority ethnic groups to come to limelight on African cultural tourism products within the region / nation.¹⁵ What this suggest is that, there are intellectual cultural identities of cultural tourism products within an ethnic groups in a region whose cultural values on morals and political influence that needs to be rediscovered and sustained towards tourism potential in the digital growth of the economic.

In another observation on demerit of cultural hegemony by Mike Wayne states that the process of cultural products production and services and consumption which are distinct can be overlapping in the minority areas or within the dominance cultural groups in the regions.¹⁶ The overlapping of cultural products and dominance can be expressed as the major cultural ethnic groups ordering of human beings as well as materials and cultural oppression that suggest tribalism, nepotism and ethnicity practices that hinders economic development. In addition to this notion, Noah Delies Ovoy and Anthony L. Brown are of the view that “the ethnic groups develop solidarity among themselves in a way of reorganizing their ways of living to establish differences and cultural autonomy.”¹⁷

In our observations on the hegemony theory, however, the cultural hegemony theory on cultural tourism products is the most reasonable and concrete notion that speaks on African ethnical state/ nation. In other words, the theory as propagated by Antonio Gramsci recognizes every state / ethnic group to be ethnical in as much as its most important functions is to raise the great mass population of a particular cultural participation in the cultural tourism products of a nation. The hegemony theory raises the cultural and moral levels of the people which correspond to the needs of the cultural tourism products productive forces for development of the tourism potentials and the economy of the nation. Also, the theory enables the stake holders and government at all levels to seek the consent of the governed and with the consent organize the cultural products of the people not based on generic and vague as it may be expressed in other instances like election. Rather, the government, stakeholders does have and seek consent of the various cultural regions to educate and harness their cultural heritages towards effectiveness and sustained economy as well digitalized their rich cultural tourism heritages for wide economic gains.

African Cultural Tourism Products and Tourism Potentials

Some African cultural tourism products with tourism potentials are selected to bring to fore the economic impact in the nation. The cultural tourism product suggests the rich cultural heritages of the people that call for digitalization of their products in digital economy.

1. Festivals as African cultural tourism product:

a. **Arugungu Fishing Festival:** Arugungu fishing festival is one of the festivals celebrated in Kebbi State of Nigeria. It is an annual festival that is observed in the month of February every year to mark the end of farming season and start of the fishing season aimed at demonstrating the indigenous way of life of Kebbi State people. Tour Nigeria assert that the festival was first celebrated in 1934 to mark the end of centuries of old hostility between the Sokoto caliphate and Kebbi kingdom.¹⁸ Thus, the fishing festival became a celebration of freedom, life and unity among Kebbi Kingdom people.

The fishing festival is a four-day cultural event which commences with agricultural antecedent, water sport display traditional Kebbawa entertainment and ends with the spectacular fishing competition in the Mata Fadam River.

Prior to the commencement of the fishing festival, the custodian of the river „Sarkin Ruwa“ ensures the river is safe by performing sacrifices to the river divinity to gain its permission.¹⁹ The sacrifices dispel the crocodiles and other harmful water creatures resident in the river and invite all the fishes in the rivers connected to Mata Fada river for the festival. The Matan Fada River is a source of pride to the people of Arugungu, it serves as a source of food and irrigation for their farm lands. The river is about 50 meters wide and about 50 feet deep.

Over 50,000 fishermen from northern Nigeria and surrounding countries participate in the Arugungu fishing festival annually.²⁰ As the fishing festival commence, the Sarkin Ruwa and the drummers move to and fro on the mata fada river on their canoes, entertaining the fishermen as they search the river for the winning Giwan Ruwa. Giwan Ruwa fish from the Mata Fadan river can weigh up to 75 kilograms. The fisherman with the biggest catch wins the competition. The mammoth crowd that participates in the fishing festival of Arugungu depicts tourism potential cultural product from the northern region of Nigeria. If well harnessed, it has the potential of enhancing the economy of the nation.

b. **Aluu Egelege festival:** The Aluu *egelege* (wrestling) festival is one of festivals celebrated by Aluu people in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. The *egelege* (wrestling) festival is celebrated in honour of a divinity „*Ogbagorogo*‘ whom it was narrated inspired a hunter that taught the people on how to play the drums and act of wrestling (Anoriochi Ogwunka).²¹

The wrestling festival commences in the month of October every year. It is a festival that lasts for nine (9) weeks with the nine (9) communities: Omuike, Omuoda, Mbodo, Omuchiorlu, Omuoko, Omuokiri, Omuigwe, Omuawhunwo and Omunhechi taking turns every week to end the festival on first week in December every year. The unique features of the *egelege* is that the festival marks the end of the year and beginning of another farming year. Wrestling philosophical songs are sung during the festival have reflecting antecedents of individuals or community in the past with the aim of instilling good morals relationship that fosters brotherhood among the people. The chief drummer, uses the sound of his drum to communicate to the wrestlers on what to know and do to defeat their opponents during the contest.

Massive crowd from other communities in Aluu and outside Aluu grace the wrestling festival in each week of a particular community schedule for the wrestling. Leisure and other recreational entertainments are performed to make guests to the wrestling festival a memorable experience whereby showcasing the tourism potential in the wrestling, a cultural product.

c. **Osun festival:** The Osun festival is one of the festivals celebrated among the Yoruba ethnic group that takes place in August every year in Osogbo, Osun state of Nigeria. As narrated by Bruce Feiler, „Osun festival is celebrated to appreciate the goddess of fertility Osun.²³ It is celebrated with the aim to renew the contract between human beings and the divine. In other words, the goddess sacred grove. Thus, the festival begins with a lamp-lighting ceremony in the street of Osogbo with a 14-year-old girl carrying the lamp and process to the sacred grove shrine where rituals with the sacred objects carried by the *Arugba* (the votary maid) are conducted. The priests and priestess wear white robes in honour of Osun, the Orisa (deity) of fertility. They plait their hair in the traditional way of *Olorisa* (those initiated in a Yoruba divinity). The brass or bronze bell they use when offering prayers to Osun is called „*aaja*“ and the sound of it serves to draw the attention of the goddess. Many ritual and sacrifice items are made of copper alloy symbolizing the river deity. The Osun river is said to have healing properties and is called the water of life.²⁴ It is believed traditionally that the Osun river is sacred and that the Orisa helps those that take the water called *agbo* by devotees to perfect healing of sicknesses and fertilization of the womb of women seeking for children. Osun festivals, last for 14 days in Osogbo with an annual participant of one hundred thousand people. This depicts cultural tourism potential from the cultural products that can boost the tourism industry in Nigeria with enormous economic impact on the revenue of the state, region and nation at large.

2. Craft as Cultural Tourism Product: Discuss on this section focuses on Igbo Ukwu and Benin crafts. In Carolyn Phinzy remark, Igbo Ukwu craft represent the ancestral legacy of the Igbo /Igbo people in Nigeria.²⁵ The craft include ceremonial vessels, pot stands, jewelry, and various ornamental regalia with incorporated symbolism that showcases the 9th -11th century C.E civilization among the Igbo ethnic group in Nigeria. On the Benin craft, Philip Peek writes that craft work is grouped under three levels. Those skilled artist that serves in Oba’s Palace that produces brass, Ivory, wood sculptures, embroidered textiles and leather fans for the Oba, his chiefs and priests.²⁶ Outside the palace, artist exist in the villages and are specialized in producing a particular crafts and items for their community own use. While the women craft is vivid in pottery which has remained as women specialization in some villages in Benin. It is believed that the supernatural forms the basis for the Benin craft making inspirations. Thus, Khana Academy avers that “artists seek guidance and protection against accidents and witchcraft and each craft has its moral teachings which inculcate believe morals and a well-coordinated indigenous society among the Benin.”²⁷

3. Clothing as Cultural Tourism Product: Traditional African clothing represents one of, if not the biggest symbols of the continents rich cultural product heritage and diversity. Chidera Anthony asserts that across the continent, different ethnic groups have their identifying traditional African clothing for occasions, traditional festivals, and special events.²⁸ In other words, clothing as a cultural product fosters reflection of the traditional society and the status of certain individuals or groups within an ethnic group as well enables one to connect to his or her roots in the community, state, nation and outside the nation.

The table below gives credence to the impact of African clothing on the people.

	AFRICAN CLOTHES	LOCATION WHERE THEY ARE WORN	PURPOSE OF WEARING THE CLOTHES
a	Dashiki	Mostly in West African and in Kenya and Tanzania	Associated Muslim wears
b	Kente	Ghana: Ashanti and Ewe people	Ghanian wears as traditional clothes
c	Iro ati Buba	Yoruba Nigeria	Traditional outfit for women from Yoruba
d	Boubou	Senegal	Traditional clothes for Senegalese men and women
e	Kanzu (white or cream clothes)	Burundi, Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Rwanda, Uganda etc.	Worn by men in African Great Lakes Region.
f	Habesha Kennis	Addis Ababa Ethiopia	Traditional clothing belonging to Habesha women of Ethiopia
g	Djellaba	North African Countries	Worn by Maghreb region for religious festivals and other occasion
h	Shuka (African Blanket)	Tanzania and Kenya Maasai people	Clothes worn before the colonization by Scottish
i	Dashiki	Ewe people of Ghana	A unisex traditional clothing
j	Isidwaba	South Africa	Traditional cloth worn by Zulu married women

k	Isiagu	Igbo people of Nigeria	Status symbol among the Igbo men for formal occasion
l	Toghu/Atoghu	Bamileke people of North Westhern Cameroon	Traditional attire suite for investiture, traditional carnation and other festivals

Source: Canva African vibes

The few explored African cultural tourism products indicate that the various ethnic groups and regions are endowed with rich cultural tourism heritages. The cultural tourism products are hegemonic, viable in tourism development for communities, states and nations digital economy derive if digitalized.

Cultural Tourism Products in the Digital Growth of the Economy

The technological revolution the world has witnessed few decades ago, permeate all sectors of human transactions: religion economic, politics, social relationship. On economic perspective, digitalization as remarked by Santander, entails the “use of information technology to create or adopt to market or consume goods and services”.²⁹ The goods and services that are cultural products from communities, ethnic groups and regions enhance cultural tourism potentials that are consumed electronically. This buttressed Cooper C. et al earlier listing the electronic devices engaged in the technological revolution as “information technologies which include: computers, video text and teledex, telephones /fares, management information system, moderns, multimedia kiosk, computer networks, the internets, satellites and wireless communication system”.³⁰

The implication on the use of the digital devices on cultural products indicates how cultural tourism products if well harnessed enhances huge financial patronage on the economy via cultural tourism goods and services consumptions to the communities, states and nation. These digital devices that aids the information communication technology operations in nations of the world, are in no doubt vital in cultural tourism products and tourism potentials development of Nigeria and by extension Africa towards boosting and enhancing the economic and services impacts on cultural products goods and services. In the same vein, the engagement of cultural tourism products on the digital devices, have tremendous impact on the economic growth of the nation Nigeria.

Some of the economic impacts of cultural tourism products on the digital devices in the economic growth, are the demand on cultural tourism products by various electronic media organization like television groups, which have several segments: Africa Magic, Epic, Africa Magic Family, Africa Magic Showcase, Africa Magic Igbo, Yoruba and Hausa, Rok I and Rok 2 television etc. the growth in television digital devices in Nigeria economy in the late 1980s and early 1990s was as a result of the affluence cultural tourism products showcased in the electronic devices. The electronic devices showcase the rich cultural products heritages of various ethnic groups and regions in Nigeria. The cultural products are harnessed by Nollywood entertainment group, individual and organizational groups on cultural tourism potentials in the nation. Thus billions of naira are been reported as revenue generated from the cultural tourism products showcased on television digital devices by the groups which have boosted the gross domestic production of the nation.

Apart from state owned television organisations, individual group also owned the electronic streaming platforms. These are vivid in soap opera from actors and actresses drawn from all nooks and crannies of the nation on several digital electronic platforms educating the populace on rich cultural tourism products in Nigeria. Thus, this enhances digital growth of the economy. This in no doubt, points to growth on digital devices usage as a result of the abundant cultural tourism products streaming on those digital devices. The use of the digital devices on the cultural tourism products enables communities, regions and ethnic groups to comprehend what the tourists and market requires of their cultural tourism products, delivery of the products to all classes of tourists in increasing order and developing their heritages for maximum satisfaction and patronage towards the economy growth. Similar Africa cultural tourism products on digital growth of the economy, finds its expression

pronounced in some African countries. For instance, in Ghana, too many electronic platforms are created to air Ghana rich cultural heritages. These cultural heritages are showcased in the free to air television channels in addition to Gallywood film industry. This point to rich African cultural tourism products in the digital growth of the economy of some African nations.

What it then implies, is the wide spread of various cultural tourism products to far coverage and tourism market, digital market (e-market), creating an awareness of the cultural products, for tourist visit and participation on the cultural heritage celebrations and spending money on the cultural goods and services. The digitalization also markets the cultural products destination for further economic ventures by tourists and host tourist destination. With the placement of cultural tourism products on digital equipment, communities, regions and nations explores areas cooperation can enhance cultural tourism products supply chains. This allows people with similar cultural tourism products heritage to share their cultural products and form a synergy to each other in tourism potentials development. The synergy enables communities with lesser manpower and cultural skills to synergies with communities that are pronounced in cultural tourism products in increasing the cultural impacts of the productions in tourism towards increasing and acquisition of new ideas.

The new ideas which are vital in economic dynamisms and growth are aimed at ensuring tourist satisfaction in tourism destinations. This enables the tourists to have leisure and recreations, and experience that are memorable in tourism operations that encourages repeat visit and wider publication on the cultural tourism products and tourism destination. As expressed by Terry Lovell on use-value, he asserts the “ability of a utility or usefulness of a commodity to satisfy some human want when the commodity is consumed or used”.³¹ The repeat visit and publication by tourists, opens the state and nation for economic exploration and constant financial flow in the economy of the national job opportunities. In application of the cultural tourism products on digital equipment: computer, android phones etc, enables the people to understand how to improve profitability and yields from a particular cultural tourism product. The application of the cultural products on phones and computers increases digital participation of individual, communities, regions on economic activity of the states and nation. This ensures the effectiveness of the cultural tourism products towards greater profitability on the cultural products.

Branding and packaging of cultural heritage products on digital channels vis-à-vis WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Google, You Tube etc., encourages consumers /tourists on line to package the products of their choice themselves, offering of discount and inducements for multiple cultural tourism product purchases. The branding and packaging could be the community’s festivals, cultural music /songs, cuisines, crafts, historical sites / buildings, natural endowments land scape and uniqueness of the community / region for tourist visit and attracting investors for investment and development of the state and region. This explains why Poon Buhalis asserted that “branding and packaging on digital devices encourages greater tailoring of products to meet individual tourist needs on cultural product goods and services and adequate participation in the economy of the host tourist destinations”.

Closely to branding and packaging of cultural tourism products on digital equipment are the management of destination image of the host communities, states and nation towards economic growth. What this entails is the use of the digital devices to inform and create better image of the communities to be peaceful, safe and hospitable for tourism and visitors to visit for leisure, recreation or business purposes. The act then facilitates the coordination development and production and delivery of the destination cultural tourism products for effective business operations in the economy on a peaceful environment.

Although, the adoption of digital devices on the cultural products in economic drive poses its own challenges. The onslaught Cyber Crime on the internet activities by fraudsters and some criminals is indeed a challenge on communities, states and nation gaining bond maximizing the financial gains from the cultural tourism products. The invention of new information communication technologies poses a challenge on usage of digital devices. In the past, it has been 1,2,3 and 4 Generation devices and network. At the moment 5G (Fifth Generation) device and network is in the market economy perhaps newer technologies might emerge and pose

difficulty in operating them. The technological literate level among the practitioners of the cultural tourism products might be very low and ignorant of the digital operation in economic development. In most cases, the communities and individuals are naive or feign ignorant on the economic values of their cultural tourism products heritages and its tourism potentials towards growth and development of the community, state and nation's economy.

That notwithstanding, Terry Lovell States that cultural tourism product on digital devices drive the economy of the state and nation to surplus-values. The labour power engaged in creating, producing cultural tourism products and buying of advertisement time in digital devices and the ability of the cultural programmes to attract tourists enhances the sale of the advertised cultural products by given the producer access to the audience watching / patronizing the cultural tourism products programme. Thus, the cultural tourism product becomes a boost in the growth of digital economy of the state/nation.

Conclusion

In concluding the study on African cultural tourism products in the digital growth of the economy, Nigeria and African are endowed with rich cultural products heritages from the various components that constitute the nation and continent. The cultural hegemony enhancing bonding and cultural identities through the expression of various cultural products of the people. Digitalization of the cultural products provides instant access, interactive multimedia information and a greater degree of interactivity at the consumer's convenience on the cultural tourism products goods and services. More so, the digitalization of the cultural products, allows the fast distribution of media information on the product to tourists and other consumers. The digitalization displays graphic data, videos, images and sounds of the cultural tourism products and as well open up new marketing communication channels for the tourism industry and economic development and growth.

Thus, the digitalization of the cultural tourism products via the technological devices aforementioned fosters abundance of the African cultural tourism products on the digital economy market of states and nations. The various ethnic groups cultural heritage identity are recognized and cherished as well government at all levels leverages on the cultural tourism products towards sustaining tourism potentials of the communities, states and nation. The act of cultural tourism products digitalization becomes a path way for the state and nation economic growth development and a continuity of cultural identity of the communities, states, nations and Africa at large.

Recommendations

1. Communities, stakeholders and States should have the statistics of their cultural tourism products heritages and identify the heritages that have tourism potentials and economic impacts.
2. There should be adequate sensitization on cultural tourism products values as to enable communities, and government at all levels cherish their heritage and pay due attention on its development.
3. The need to create the World Wide Web (www) platform for effective marketing and awareness of affluence cultural product by streaming on the cultural products becomes inevitable. This will enhance economic growth on the cultural products and create tourism awareness and attraction on various tourism destinations.
4. Adequate legislation should be done on the use of website to check mate unhealthy practices on the internet.
5. A coordinated collaboration between the cultural tourism host destination and all electronic media organisations and e-markets platforms for effective streaming of the cultural products.

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